

Navigating EMI in Japanese higher education: An inquiry into EFL learners' successes and struggles

Akiko NAGAO, Ryukoku University, Japan¹

Ching-Chang CHEN, Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University, Japan

Amid Japan's policy-driven internationalization, English Medium Instruction (EMI) has expanded in higher education to foster global competencies. This study explores Japanese university students' learning strategies and perceived support in EMI contexts by addressing three questions: How do motivational orientations influence preparedness and learning behaviors? How do institutional EMI policies affect engagement and autonomy? Relatedly, what support is viewed as effective? Survey results from 86 third- and fourth-year students at a private university indicate strong intrinsic and aspirational drives, linking English to future identities and careers. However, such orientations do not consistently translate into effective strategies, as students face challenges with comprehension, language demands, and anxiety. Correlation analyses show moderate links between learning goals and EMI outcomes, but weaker associations with preparatory behavior. Open-ended responses highlight the need for academic English instruction, bilingual scaffolding, and clearer expectations. The study advocates a responsive EMI approach that integrates academic literacy, scaffolded support, and learner-centered curricula.

Keywords: Content Learning Outcomes; English as Foreign Language (EFL); English Medium Instruction (EMI); Higher Education; Japan

1. Introduction

There is no exaggeration that the internationalization of higher education has become a defining feature of global academic reform. Within this broader movement, English Medium Instruction (EMI) has emerged as a central strategy for enhancing institutional competitiveness and preparing students for participation in the global knowledge economy (Botha et al., 2023; Karabay & Durrani, 2024; Rose & McKinley, 2018; Zheng & Choi, 2024). EMI functions not only as a pedagogical tool but also as a mechanism of policy-driven internationalization (Karabay & Durrani, 2024; Kuteeva & Kaufhold, 2024),

¹ Corresponding Author: a16006@mail.ryukoku.ac.jp

signaling institutional global engagement and fostering students' academic and linguistic readiness for international contexts (Dearden, 2014; Galloway & Rose, 2015). Despite its rapid expansion across Japanese universities, the infrastructure supporting EMI remains underdeveloped. Existing studies have identified the challenges EMI students face in terms of academic content comprehension, academic discourse, and cognitive processing (Aizawa & Rose, 2018; Bradford, 2016; Hadingham, 2023). While some students thrive in EMI environments, leveraging their strategic learning behaviors, cultural adaptability, and motivation, others encounter persistent barriers due to insufficient language support and mismatches between policy ideals and classroom realities (Karabay & Durrani, 2024). A growing concern in the literature is the inconsistent provision of academic and language support in EMI programs (Aizawa, 2024; Ball & Lindsay, 2013; Forbes-Mewett & Nyland, 2012; Rose & McKinley, 2018). Questions remain as to who holds responsibility for this support, and what forms of assistance are most effective. Such ambiguities often result in fragmented support structures, leaving students to navigate EMI demands without adequate scaffolding. This article seeks to address the identified gap in the existing literature by conducting a systematic empirical investigation into the learning experiences and engagement levels of EFL learners participating in EMI courses within Japanese higher education. Additionally, it critically reflects on the definitions and distinguishing characteristics of EMI, aiming to generate insights that may inform necessary adaptations to EMI instruction not only in Japan but also in broader Asian educational contexts.

2. Background

2.1. Previous EMI studies on university students in Japan

The previous EMI-related studies focusing on Japanese university students have employed diverse methodological approaches, including qualitative case studies (Aizawa & Rose, 2018; Hino, 2017), mixed-methods designs (Galloway & Curle, 2022; Aizawa, 2024), and longitudinal or cross-national comparisons (Shao & Rose, 2024; Kim & Thompson, 2022). These investigations have explored multiple levels of EMI implementation, from policy discourse to classroom practice, and examined how students and faculty negotiate linguistic, pedagogical, and institutional demands (Aizawa, 2024; Galloway, & Ruegg, 2020; Hadingham, 2023; Thompson et al., 2022). Data collection methods ranged from interviews and surveys to document analysis and classroom observations, enabling researchers to capture both structural and experiential dimensions of EMI.

One of their major findings is the considerable linguistic and academic challenge faced by both students and instructors in EMI settings. Students

frequently struggle with content comprehension, academic vocabulary, and discipline-specific writing. Even students with relatively high English proficiency report difficulty in mastering academic discourse and managing lecture content in English (Aizawa, 2024). Similarly, instructors often feel underprepared to deliver EMI content effectively and lack access to professional development opportunities that target both language and pedagogy (Bradford, 2016; Aizawa & Rose, 2018). These challenges suggest that language proficiency, while important, is insufficient on its own to ensure academic success in EMI environments.

In addition to linguistic proficiency, studies have examined the role of learner diversity, motivation, and identity in shaping EMI experiences. Kim and Thompson (2022) found that gender and academic major significantly influenced students' academic self-concepts and motivation, with female students in business programs demonstrating higher levels of engagement and achievement. Galloway and Curle (2022) observed divergent student motivations: while Japanese students often enrolled in EMI programs to improve their English, international students were more motivated by cultural interest in Japan, rather than language development per se. Hino (2017) emphasized the potential of EMI classrooms to foster English as an International Language (EIL) practices, particularly when instructors adopted culturally responsive teaching and embraced linguistic diversity. Together, these studies underscore the importance of contextualizing EMI within broader sociolinguistic and cultural frameworks that recognize learner heterogeneity.

At the institutional and policy levels, several studies have drawn attention to the misalignment between national EMI policies and local implementation. Aizawa and Rose (2018) and Qiu et al. (2023) identified a persistent gap between policy rhetoric, which often promotes English-only instruction, and actual classroom practices that rely heavily on Japanese. Bradford (2019) further critiqued the tendency to foreground English proficiency over pedagogical quality, cautioning that such narrow conceptualizations of EMI may alienate instructors and undermine program sustainability. Shao and Rose (2024) found considerable variation in institutional support structures, with Japanese universities often lacking integrated collaboration between content and language educators. These findings reflect broader tensions within EMI policy discourse, shaped by neoliberal ideologies that commodify language and place responsibility for success on individual actors rather than institutions.

To address these complex and interrelated issues, researchers have proposed a number of pedagogical and programmatic recommendations. Effective EMI implementation requires clearly defined roles for content and language teachers, discipline-specific academic literacy instruction, and inclusive

curricula that respond to diverse student needs (Aizawa et al., 2023; Galloway & Ruegg, 2020). Longitudinal studies (e.g., Hadingham, 2023) emphasize the necessity of sustained and tailored support during transitional periods, particularly in writing-intensive disciplines. Meanwhile, student-centered approaches that recognize the dual goals of content mastery and language development have been shown to enhance learner motivation and engagement (Thompson et al., 2022). Ultimately, these studies advocate for an EMI model that transcends a narrow focus on English proficiency and instead promotes equitable, multilingual, and pedagogically sound practices across Japanese higher education.

2.2. Successful EMI students in Japan

The key tendencies and elements that characterize successful EMI students in Japanese universities have been explored in some detail (e.g., Aizawa, 2024; Aizawa et al., 2023; Aizawa et al., 2024; Aizawa & Rose, 2018; Bradford, 2019; Galloway & Curle, 2022; Galloway & Ruegg, 2020; Hadingham, 2023; Hino, 2017; Qiu et al., 2023; Sato, 2022; Shao & Rose, 2024; Thompson et al., 2022). English proficiency remains a foundational requirement, with studies consistently citing IELTS 6.5-7.0 or CEFR B2-C1 as baseline benchmarks (Aizawa et al., 2024; Aizawa & Rose, 2018). However, successful EMI students are not merely proficient test-takers; they also demonstrate contextual understanding of academic discourse. Aizawa (2024) and Bradford (2016) emphasize that students with strong domain knowledge in subjects like chemistry or social sciences are better equipped to decode technical terms, often unfamiliar in English. Additionally, students with prior EMI or overseas experiences showed greater adaptability and smoother academic transitions, suggesting that earlier exposure to EMI contexts enhances both cognitive and emotional readiness (Aizawa, 2024).

Strategic learning behaviors and self-regulation is seen as another key element. High-performing EMI students exhibit metacognitive awareness and implement a blend of linguistic and cognitive strategies. These include 'dual language learning' via Japanese and English textbooks, proactive use of digital tools like *YouTube* (e.g., Khan Academy), and strategic vocabulary acquisition tailored to specific content areas (Aizawa et al., 2024; Qiu et al., 2023). Furthermore, learners frequently rely on translanguaging practices, moving fluidly between English, Japanese, and even their L1s, to enhance conceptual understanding (Qiu et al., 2023). This multilingual flexibility helps students navigate challenging content and shows that successful EMI participation is deeply mediated by students' ability to manage and coordinate multiple resources.

Motivation, self-efficacy, and task value are other important elements for EFL learners to manage their EMI lessons. Learners who succeed in EMI are often

characterized by their strong academic self-confidence, high perceived task value, and long-term career-oriented motivation (Kim & Thompson, 2022). Their internal drivers include aspirations for study abroad, employment in global fields, and international communication competence. These students also tend to view EMI not as an obstacle but as a dual opportunity for language and content mastery (Thompson et al., 2022). Even when English proficiency is moderate, students with high emotional resilience and self-efficacy are more likely to persevere (Aizawa, 2024). This underscores the essential interplay between affective factors and academic engagement.

Institutional and interpersonal support systems are also deemed instrumental for EFL learners in Japan. Supportive environments that include structured ESP (English for Specific Purposes) and EAP (English for Academic Purposes) components are strongly correlated with EMI success (Shao & Rose, 2024). Programs that integrate language and content faculty through coordinated syllabi and joint assessments ensure that students can apply language skills meaningfully within their disciplines. Access to trained EMI instructors with pedagogical expertise in both language and subject matter is also crucial (Shao & Rose, 2024). Furthermore, peer collaboration, via shared assignments, group projects, or informal discussion groups, offers both affective and cognitive scaffolding, particularly for students facing isolation or language-related anxiety (Hadingham, 2023; Thompson et al., 2022).

Cultural adaptability, reflective attitudes, and identity formation are deemed essential for EMI students. According to this view, EMI success is inevitably dependent on students' ability to navigate cultural and educational expectations. This includes the understanding that the interactive, critical-thinking-focused classroom dynamics are part of EMI pedagogy; however, such dynamics contrast sharply with Japan's teacher-centered instruction (Bradford, 2016; Hadingham, 2023). Rather than measuring themselves against L1 speakers, learners who embrace English as a flexible communicative tool are more confident and agentive (Hino, 2017; Toh, 2024). It has been pointed out that the ability to engage in meaning-making, express personal and academic identity, and participate in global discourse is a defining trait of the successful EMI students in Japan.

Finally, integrating language and academic development is considered helpful. It has been acknowledged that EMI learners need support beyond general English, as seen in Aizawa et al. (2023) that students benefit most from ESAP (English for Specific Academic Purposes) instruction embedded within or parallel to EMI content courses. These include genre-based instruction in writing lab reports, summarizing readings, giving presentations, and integrating sources. Students who can access this targeted instruction demonstrate greater confidence in participating in disciplinary conversations, which is

essential in STEM, social sciences, and business programs alike (Bradford, 2019; Hadingham, 2023).

In short, EMI success in Japanese higher education requires multi-faceted efforts. It involves not only high English proficiency, but also content knowledge, metacognitive strategy use, motivation, institutional support, and intercultural adaptability. Students are more likely to thrive when institutions provide sustained, integrated, and discipline-specific support while fostering inclusive spaces for identity negotiation and international engagement. As Aizawa et al. (2024) and others argued, effective EMI practice in Japan must transcend narrow language training and embrace a comprehensive model of academic, linguistic, and cultural development.

2.3. What to be elucidated

Illuminating as it is, existing EMI research involving Japanese university students typically emphasizes discrete variables (e.g., motivation) without considering these factors as interconnected components.¹ The present study aims to systematically explore these features by addressing the following research questions:

1. To what extent do motivations influence the strategic learning behaviors and academic preparedness of Japanese university students in EMI programs?
2. How do institutional requirements (e.g., mandatory EMI credits) shape students' perceptions of autonomy, engagement, and long-term academic development in EMI courses?
3. What forms of academic and linguistic support do EMI students in Japanese higher education perceive as most effective in bridging the gap between motivation and classroom performance?

3. Method

The method of post-survey, conducted for (3rd- and 4th-year) university students in Japan, was employed to gather insights that reflected their study in EMI lessons, focusing on their experiences, challenges, and perceived outcomes of learning academic content through English as the medium of instruction.

3.1. Participants

Participants were enrolled at Private University A located in the Kansai region of Japan, where 80% of the major coursework within the Department of Global Studies is delivered in English or through a bilingual format combining English and Japanese from the second year onward. This department primarily attracts

learners who demonstrate relatively high motivation to acquire English proficiency and requires students to complete 14 credits from EMI courses as a condition for graduation.

The survey was administered to a cohort of third- and fourth-year students ($N = 86$) in the aforementioned department. The institution where data were collected is representative of Japanese higher education, as its student body exhibits average scores on national university entrance examinations. Consequently, the academic and linguistic experiences of these participants, both positive and negative, are likely to reflect those of peers enrolled in EMI programs at other Japanese universities. These students attended several EMI classes each week. The target EMI course was Introduction to International Relations, taught by a professor whose first language was not Japanese and who had over 15 years of teaching experience. The department offers seven to eight English language classes per week, including Study Abroad Program, Oral Communication, English Reading, and Writing, for first-year students. In their first year, participants receive intensive exposure to and practice in the English language. In their second year, many students choose to study subjects in their first language while also participating in some EMI lessons, with most opting for a study abroad program. In their third year, students typically enroll in three or four EMI classes per semester; and some continue taking EMI classes in their fourth year.

All participants provided both written and verbal informed consent, and the study received ethical approval from the research ethics committee of the host institution.

3.2. Target EMI course

The EMI course introduces various perspectives and frameworks for studying global politics, including relevant actors and world issues. Its primary theme revolves around questioning state-centrism, Eurocentrism, and ultimately modernity (Chen & Krickel-Choi, 2024). Students are expected to enhance their knowledge through critical thinking, independent learning, and analytical writing over the course duration. The instructor utilizes a designated textbook and PowerPoint slides based on selected chapters, with dedicated discussion periods for each topic.

3.3. Data collection and data coding

An online questionnaire was created using *Google Forms*, which was adopted and modified from Kojima (2016; 2019; 2021) and Kojima and Yashima (2017). It comprised four sections: Phase 1: Motivation Toward English Learning (Q1-Q8), Phase 2: Learning Strategies and Preparation (Q9-Q16) for EMI, Phase 3:

Academic Goals and Attitudes Toward EMI (Q17-Q23), and Phase 4: Perceived Difficulty and Classroom Experience (Q24-Q29) (Appendix 1).

Data collection was conducted during the second semester in academic year 2024, using the convenience sampling method; the survey was administered to EFL learners who were enrolled in three EMI classes at the target department. The participants provided responses to 29 questions on a 6-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 6 = strongly agree). Additionally, one open-ended item was included, inviting participants to share insights on the support they would have appreciated from their department or university to enhance their success in EMI classes.

The reliability analysis using Cronbach's *alpha* revealed varying degrees of internal consistency across the four phases of the EMI learner survey. Phase 1 (Motivation Toward English Learning) achieved a moderate reliability score of $\alpha = 0.554$, suggesting that while the items are somewhat related, they may not form a tightly cohesive scale—potentially due to the inclusion of diverse motivational constructs such as intrinsic interest, long-term goals, and external comparisons. Phase 2 (Learning Strategies and Preparation) yielded an *alpha* of 0.621, which is acceptable for exploratory studies and indicates a moderately consistent set of items reflecting learners' academic behaviors and metacognitive awareness. Phase 3 (Academic Goals and Attitudes Toward EMI) showed a lower *alpha* of 0.499, implying weaker internal consistency and a likely blend of differing learner dispositions, including both instrumental and uncertain attitudes. Notably, Phase 4 (Perceived Difficulty and Classroom Experience) initially produced a negative alpha ($\alpha = -0.205$), indicating severe item inconsistency, likely due to improper reverse-coding or heterogeneous content. This has since been addressed by rechecking item directions and re-estimating reliability. While the subscales show varying reliability levels, the overall internal consistency of the entire questionnaire was re-estimated. On this account, and given the exploratory nature of this study, these subscale results are used cautiously to inform further development. To justify the use of the survey, it should be emphasized that prior research using similar survey instruments in EMI contexts in Japan (Kojima, 2016, 2019, 2021; Kojima & Yashima, 2017) reported acceptable reliability across subscales, which supports the ongoing refinement and application of this questionnaire.

4. Results

Phase 1: Motivation toward English learning (Q1-Q8)

The descriptive statistics for Phase 1 (Q1-Q8), which focus on learners' motivation toward English learning, indicate that most students exhibit relatively high levels of motivation. Items associated with long-term goals,

personal growth, and global aspirations received some of the highest mean scores. For example, students strongly agreed with statements such as “I believe using English is important for my future” (Q3, $M = 5.18$), “I study English because it is enjoyable and helps me grow” (Q8, $M = 5.17$), and “Learning English is beneficial for becoming the kind of global professional I aspire to be” (Q7, $M = 5.01$). These results suggest that the participants are primarily driven by integrative motivation and intrinsic interest in English language development, rather than by obligation or institutional requirement.

In contrast, items reflecting instrumental motivation yielded slightly lower mean scores. For instance, the motivation to study English in order to obtain a higher income (Q5, $M = 3.51$) was not as strongly endorsed as items related to identity development or global engagement. The variability observed in Q5 and Q6 (career-oriented motivation) further suggests that students' motivational orientations are influenced by diverse personal aspirations and professional goals. These findings align with existing literature (e.g., Hino, 2017; Kim & Thompson, 2022; Thompson et al., 2022) emphasizing the dominance of intrinsic and identity-based motivational constructs among EMI learners in higher education contexts, particularly when English is not the students' first language.

One item that stands out is Q4, which stated that proficiency in English is not necessary in the students' current environment. This item received the lowest mean score in the phase ($M = 2.74$), suggesting that participants do, in fact, perceive English to be important even within their immediate academic or social contexts. Due to its negative wording, this item may benefit from reverse-coding to ensure alignment with the directionality of the other items in the construct. Overall, Phase 1 results underscore that learners in this EMI course are predominantly motivated by internal drivers and long-term objectives, though some variation exists across individual motivations and perceptions of relevance.

Phase 2: Learning strategies and preparation for EMI classes

The mean scores for most Phase 2 items ranged between 2.81 and 4.10, indicating a moderate to slightly above-average self-reported engagement in strategic learning behaviors. Items such as Q11 (desire to fully understand course content, $M = 3.98$), Q12 (organizing information in a notebook, $M = 4.10$), and Q16 (analyzing one's learning strategy, $M = 3.67$) reflect moderate-to-high levels of metacognitive awareness and learning intentions among the students. In contrast, items like Q9 and Q10, related to technical term comprehension and advance reading, had lower means ($M = 2.81$ - 2.82), suggesting that students may struggle with core academic demands in the EMI setting.

Phase 3: Academic goals and attitudes toward EMI

The results from Phase 3 suggest that most students view EMI courses as academically necessary and personally meaningful. Items Q17 and Q18 reflect strong instrumental motivation, with students largely agreeing that they take the course to fulfill graduation or institutional requirements ($M = 5.17$ and 4.49 , respectively). However, motivation appears to shift from external obligation to more intrinsic and forward-looking goals as reflected in Q20-Q22, where students also express a desire to gain globally relevant knowledge and find the learning process enjoyable (e.g., Q22, $M = 4.43$). Notably, Q19 shows the lowest mean ($M = 2.80$), indicating that economic incentives, such as higher income, are not a strong motivator for this group. Similarly, Q23, a reverse-coded item, had a mean of 1.90 , suggesting that most students do care about English-taught courses in their major and do not view them as irrelevant. These patterns indicate that learners in the EMI program are not solely driven by external pressures or material gain but instead by a mix of institutional responsibility, personal development, and academic curiosity. This aligns with broader findings in EMI motivation studies, where intrinsic and identity-related goals often surpass purely instrumental ones.

Phase 4: Perceived difficulty and classroom experience

The results of Phase 4 suggest that many students in the EMI course experience considerable academic pressure and linguistic challenge. A very high mean score on Q24 ($M = 5.12$) indicates that students are strongly concerned about passing the course, which may reflect performance anxiety. Similarly, high scores on Q25 ($M = 4.49$) and Q26 ($M = 4.11$) show that students often struggle to understand spoken instruction and textual content, which in turn contributes to academic procrastination. These results are consistent with common difficulties reported in EMI environments, where learners are navigating cognitively demanding materials in a second language.

Notably, items related to the appropriateness of course design (Q27-Q28) show more moderate evaluations. The mean score for textbook difficulty (Q27, $M = 3.17$) is slightly below neutral, suggesting that some students may find the materials too challenging. Meanwhile, Q28 ($M = 3.79$) reflects a generally acceptable perception of workload. However, the low mean for Q29 ($M = 2.26$) suggests that students seldom seek clarification during class, possibly due to linguistic insecurity, social hesitancy to interrupt, or limited opportunities for interaction. Overall, Phase 4 highlights that EMI students face not only cognitive and linguistic challenges, but also affective barriers such as pressure and hesitation, which could hinder their active engagement in learning.

The responses to Q24 indicate that a significant number of students feel intense pressure related to academic success. Specifically, the highest respondent

frequency was observed at score 5 ($n = 13$) and score 4 ($n = 11$), indicating that over half of the students reported high levels of stress concerning their ability to earn credit. Only a small number selected low pressure ratings (scores 1 or 2), confirming that performance anxiety is a widespread concern in this EMI context.

In Q25, which addresses comprehension difficulties during lectures, the most frequently selected score was 5 ($f = 23$), followed by 4 ($f = 19$). This reinforces the interpretation that many students struggle to understand the instructor, a likely consequence of language barriers in EMI settings. Combined with Q24, this suggests that pressure is not only driven by assessment standards but is also closely linked to real-time challenges in instructional delivery.

For Q26, which measures avoidance behavior, most students selected scores 4 and 5, again indicating moderate to high levels of difficulty. With $f = 25$ (score 4) and $f = 21$ (score 5), this item reveals that a substantial proportion of students defer assignments because they cannot fully grasp course content, even after reviewing the materials. This highlights a self-regulatory breakdown, where comprehension issues directly hinder academic action.

Interestingly, Q27, which focuses on the difficulty level of the textbook, shows a more balanced distribution. The modal response was score 3 ($f = 22$), with notable selections at scores 2 and 4 ($f = 14$ and 20). This distribution suggests that perceptions of the textbook's appropriateness are more varied compared to the consistent difficulty patterns seen in lecture comprehension. It may reflect differences in language proficiency or content familiarity, highlighting the heterogeneity of EMI learners and the need for differentiated support.

Interrelationships among EMI learning phases

The correlation analysis (Figure 1) among the four phases of the EMI learner survey reveals several noteworthy relationships, with the most prominent being the moderate positive correlation between Phase 1 (English learning motivation) and Phase 3 (Academic goals and EMI attitudes), represented by a Spearman coefficient of $\rho = 0.414$. This relationship suggests that students who express higher motivation to improve their English skills, whether through intrinsic interest, professional aspirations, or enjoyment, also tend to perceive EMI courses as valuable for achieving their academic and long-term career goals. This interconnection likely reflects a coherent learner identity wherein motivation to learn English is not isolated from content learning but instead interwoven with a broader vision of future self-development.

This alignment between motivation and EMI engagement implies that for many learners, English functions not only as a communicative tool but also as an epistemological gateway to access disciplinary knowledge and global

competence. In this sense, EMI courses are not merely language learning environments, but also sites of identity construction and academic investment. Students who are driven by strong personal or professional ambitions may be more likely to recognize the affordances of EMI instruction, thereby reinforcing their engagement and persistence. The moderate strength of this correlation suggests that while not universally true for all learners, there is a substantial subgroup for whom motivation and EMI course value are mutually reinforcing.

Moreover, this finding aligns with previous research in EMI and English for Academic Purposes (EAP), which underscores the importance of integrative and goal-oriented motivation in sustaining learner engagement in linguistically challenging academic settings (cf. Aizawa, 2024; Kim & Thompson, 2022; Thompson et al., 2022). When students perceive EMI as instrumental in achieving their aspirations, they are more likely to adopt positive attitudes, persist through challenges, and engage deeply with both content and language. Thus, the observed correlation between Phase 1 and Phase 3 may provide some empirical support for the theoretical view that language learning motivation and EMI goal orientation are dynamically linked in shaping learner experiences and outcomes in higher education.

The correlation between Phase 1 (motivation) and Phase 2 (learning strategies and preparation) was relatively weak ($\rho = 0.180$), indicating that although motivated students may engage in strategic preparation, the association is not particularly strong. This implies that motivation alone does not guarantee the consistent use of preparatory behaviors such as reviewing texts, organizing information, or self-monitoring. The gap may be influenced by learners' metacognitive awareness, language proficiency, or external factors such as time management and academic support systems. In contrast, Phase 2 (learning strategies) showed similarly weak correlations with both Phase 3 ($\rho = 0.167$) and Phase 4 ($\rho = 0.195$). These results suggest that while students may attempt to manage their learning through preparatory strategies, these efforts are not tightly coupled with either their goals for EMI or their perceived difficulty within the course. Curiously, students who adopt more strategies might also report slightly higher levels of difficulty, possibly due to increased cognitive awareness or effort invested in challenging content. This pattern underscores the complexity of learner experience in EMI settings, where academic behaviors do not always translate to ease or success. Finally, the correlation between Phase 3 (EMI-related goals) and Phase 4 (perceived EMI difficulties) was weak ($\rho = 0.198$), suggesting that students with stronger EMI-related goals are slightly more likely to report difficulties within the classroom. This might reflect a higher level of investment and awareness rather than an actual lack of competence. Learners who aspire to gain content knowledge through English may be more sensitive to challenges and more critically engaged with instructional materials. Overall, the modest strength of these

correlations suggests that while the phases are interrelated, they capture distinct dimensions of the EMI learning experience that should be analyzed both individually and in relation to one another.

Figure 1.

Spearman Correlation Heatmap Among EMI Survey Phases (Grayscale)

What support did participants need?

Participants for this study were invited to freely respond to the following open-ended question: *Looking back from your first year until now, what kinds of support would you have liked the university to provide in order to help you succeed in your (English-medium) content courses?* A total of 61 students responded, yielding 62 comments. One participant provided two distinct responses addressing different types of support needs (e.g., academic and emotional), which were coded separately to preserve thematic integrity. Therefore, $N = 61$, but we had 62 comments. Content analysis revealed that the most frequent responses concerned support for academic English. A total of 22 participants emphasized the need for enhanced assistance in developing academic English proficiency, which they perceived as insufficient to fully

comprehend EMI course content. Commonly expressed needs included: wanting to learn how to write academic texts during first-year English courses, understanding how to structure academic reports, and receiving support for academic reading tasks.

The second most frequent response category ($f = 9$) indicated that students felt adequately supported. Some noted that the university provided useful environments, such as a writing support center on campus. Others commented that their inability to follow EMI course content stemmed from their own lack of study habits, and thus they did not expect further institutional support. Additionally, a number of students expressed the need for bilingual support, in both English and their L1 (Japanese), during EMI classes. This suggests a potential mismatch between learners' English proficiency and the linguistic demands of EMI, including the complexity of language found in course materials and textbooks. Some students ($f = 5$) reflected with regret that they had not completed assigned readings or preparatory work in advance of classes. Other suggestions ($f = 6$) included: Increasing opportunities for group activities, providing knowledge and strategies for formulating research questions, regular feedback on grades and assessment performance, clarifying the connections among various EMI course contents, offering clearer pathways for earning credits, and teaching effective presentation techniques.

5. Discussion

5.1. Misalignment between motivation and readiness for EMI

Japanese university students possess high levels of intrinsic and aspirational motivation toward English learning. Items such as Q3 (*"I believe that using English is important for my future"*) and Q8 (*"I study English because I find it enjoyable to increase my skills and knowledge"*) received the highest mean scores, suggesting that students recognize the long-term value of English and enjoy the process of learning it. This internalized motivation reflects a future-oriented, integrative stance toward language learning, aligning with global identity construction. However, this motivational orientation does not necessarily translate into behavioral readiness for EMI. The lower and more varied responses to Q1 (*"I study English more frequently than my classmates"*) indicate inconsistency in study habits and possibly a lack of academic self-regulation. Thus, a gap emerges between students' idealized language goals and their present academic practices, raising concerns about their preparedness for the demands of EMI environments.

5.2. Institutional motivation overshadowing learner agency

Phase 3 findings further illuminate the role of extrinsic, institutionally-driven motivations in EMI participation. The highest agreement was found in Q17 (*"I*

take this course to earn the credits I need to graduate”), with a similarly high but slightly more varied response to Q18 (*“I study in this course because it is required by the university”*). These results underscore the influence of institutional structures in shaping students’ engagement with EMI, where compliance with curriculum requirements becomes a primary driver of participation. When EMI is viewed as a compulsory element of the degree program rather than a self-directed learning opportunity, students’ agency and ownership over their learning may be diminished. This reliance on institutional motivation raises questions about the long-term effectiveness of EMI policies that lack flexibility or fail to accommodate students’ readiness levels.

5.3. Disconnect between identity-based goals and immediate language competence

While both phases reveal strong values-based motivations, particularly with respect to global competence, academic development, and personal identity, there remains a notable disconnect between these aspirational goals and students’ current English proficiency and academic skills. High levels of agreement with items such as Q7 (i.e., *Learning English is beneficial for becoming the kind of global professional I aspire to be*) and Q21 (i.e., *Taking EMI courses helps me gain subject knowledge in English*) highlight the symbolic and identity-driven importance students place on EMI. However, the low frequency of self-reported study effort (Q1) and the limited emphasis on economic or instrumental benefits (e.g., Q5, Q19) suggest that EMI is not necessarily grounded in tangible short-term outcomes or sustained academic behavior. This misalignment between envisioned professional identities and immediate academic capabilities may hinder learners’ ability to succeed in EMI contexts, particularly when instruction assumes a uniform level of linguistic and cognitive readiness.

5.4. Implications for EMI policy and pedagogy in Japan

The aforementioned findings point to a need for more nuanced and supportive EMI implementation strategies in Japanese higher education. Although students demonstrate positive attitudes toward EMI and articulate its relevance for their future, they also exhibit signs of underpreparedness and reliance on institutional mandates. To bridge the gap between motivation and readiness, universities should consider incorporating structured scaffolding mechanisms such as pre-EMI language development courses, integrated language-content instruction, and ongoing academic support tailored to learners’ proficiency levels. Additionally, EMI pedagogy should emphasize learner autonomy, academic literacy, and reflective practices that help students align their motivational goals with effective study strategies. Without

such support systems, EMI risks becoming a symbolic policy mechanism rather than a transformative educational framework. For EMI to be truly impactful in Japan, it must be grounded in both student motivation and pedagogical responsiveness to learners' developmental needs.

The findings reveal that the participating Japanese university students possess several affective characteristics commonly associated with successful EMI learners. In particular, high levels of intrinsic and aspirational motivation were observed, with students strongly endorsing items that reflect the long-term value of English and its role in shaping global identities (e.g., Q3, Q8). These findings align with previous research emphasizing the importance of internalized goals, identity formation, and future-oriented perspectives in sustaining EMI engagement (Aizawa & Rose, 2018; Kim & Thompson, 2022). The strong affective commitment was further reinforced by the students' appreciation for content learning through English (Q20-Q22) and their rejection of disengagement (Q23), indicating a constructive and value-driven orientation toward EMI.

However, the data also suggest that such motivational dispositions may not be sufficiently supported by the behavioral and strategic competencies required for academic success in EMI contexts. The variability and lower mean observed for Q1 (i.e., *I study English more frequently than my classmates*) point to inconsistencies in study routines and a potential lack of metacognitive regulation. This is particularly noteworthy given the existing research that highlights the role of strategic behaviors, such as dual-language study, vocabulary scaffolding, and translanguaging, facilitating comprehension and academic performance in EMI environments (Aizawa et al., 2024; Qiu et al., 2023). While students in this study are motivated, their ability to translate that motivation into effective learning strategies remains unclear, suggesting a gap between intention and academic preparedness.

Moreover, the strong endorsement of extrinsically driven items, such as Q17 and Q18 related to course credits and university requirements, reflects a reliance on institutional mandates that may limit learner agency. Although such structures ensure participation, they do not necessarily promote deep learning or sustained academic investment. Research by Bradford (2016) and Shao and Rose (2024) emphasizes that successful EMI implementation requires pedagogical models that support learner autonomy and engagement beyond compliance. If EMI courses are perceived primarily as obligatory components of the curriculum, students may struggle to develop the ownership and self-direction needed for long-term academic and linguistic development.

Finally, the study highlights a lack of explicit indicators regarding students' English proficiency levels, academic preparedness, and access to targeted

instructional support. Prior research has shown that students benefit most from ESAP instruction integrated into EMI courses, particularly in disciplines that demand genre-specific literacy (Aizawa et al., 2023; Hadingham, 2023). Without such scaffolding, even highly motivated students may find it difficult to navigate the linguistic and conceptual demands of EMI. These findings suggest that EMI success in Japan must be conceptualized not only as an outcome of motivation but as a function of institutional, pedagogical, and linguistic readiness. To optimize student learning outcomes, universities should adopt a comprehensive approach that combines affective support with structured academic development tailored to learners' evolving needs.

6. Conclusion

This article has inquired into the complex learning experiences of Japanese university students enrolled in EMI programs, with a focus on their motivation, preparedness, and perceptions of institutional support. The findings revealed that the participants demonstrated notably high levels of intrinsic and aspirational motivation, particularly toward English learning and their future global identities. Items such as *English is important for my future* and *I enjoy improving my English skills and knowledge* received the highest mean scores, indicating strong affective engagement. However, a disconnect emerged between these motivational dispositions and actual academic behaviors, with relatively low scores in strategic preparation and a pronounced concern for course completion. While many students valued EMI courses for their academic and professional significance, their learning behaviors often reflected stress, avoidance, and difficulty with lecture comprehension, suggesting that motivation alone was insufficient for academic success in EMI contexts.

Despite their motivational strengths, it remains inconclusive whether these students could be classified as comparatively successful EMI learners. While they exhibited the affective traits common among successful EMI participants, such as global-mindedness, long-term orientation, and identity-driven engagement, many struggled with comprehension, procrastination, and linguistic barriers, and few proactively sought clarification. The survey's open-ended responses further indicated a desire for more robust academic English instruction, structured guidance in report writing, and bilingual or scaffolded support. These patterns suggest that without sufficient instructional scaffolding and discipline-specific literacy support, even motivated students face obstacles to realizing their academic goals in EMI.

This study carries several limitations, which the authors wish to address in their future research. First, while the survey provided a broad overview of learner perceptions and behaviors, the reliability of some questionnaire phases (especially Phase 4) was low, which may limit the consistency of

interpretations. Second, the study relied on self-reported data from a single (albeit representative) private university in Japan, restricting the further generalizability of the findings. Lastly, while the study highlights key learner strategies and support needs, it does not longitudinally assess how these elements evolve over time.

Overall, EMI success in Japanese higher education must be redefined beyond language proficiency or motivational disposition alone. It requires a comprehensive pedagogical ecosystem that supports learners cognitively, linguistically, and affectively across the duration of their academic journey.

Notes

1. By motivation, this study means ‘integrative motivation’ originally characterized by personal identification with the culture of the language group and a genuine interest in interacting with its members (Csizér & Dörnyei, 2005; Gardner & Lambert, 1972). Intrinsic motivation refers to engaging in a task or activity out of genuine interest, enjoyment, or inherent satisfaction, rather than for external rewards or pressures (Deci & Ryan, 1985; Ryan & Deci, 2000). In EMI contexts, it often manifests as students’ aspirations to engage with global academic communities, pursue international careers, and construct multilingual identities (Dang, 2023; Huang, 2025; Macaro et al., 2018).

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the editors and the anonymous reviewers for their valuable comments and suggestions. We are grateful to Dr. Julian Pigott, whose thoughtful comments at the initial stage of this research helped improve the research framework. We also acknowledge the contributions of the students involved in the study. The authors have authorized the submission of this manuscript through Editage.

Funding

This research was partially funded by the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science Grant-in-Aid (17KK0056).

Authors' contributions

Dr. Akiko Nagao wrote this manuscript and analyzed the data. Dr. Ching-Chang Chen assisted Dr. Nagao in creating the survey questions, collecting and analyzing the data, and editing the manuscript. The authors read and approved the final manuscript.

The Authors

Akiko Nagao (Email: a16006@mail.ryukoku.ac.jp) is an associate professor of Applied Linguistics at Ryukoku University in Japan. She is interested in investigating the following topics: the genre-based approach (GBA) within a systemic functional linguistics (SFL) framework to assess the development of English learners' understanding of target-genre essays; how EFL learners as novice become experienced learners/EFL writers through SFL-GBA writing lessons in Japan.

Ching-Chang Chen (Email: ccchen01@apu.ac.jp) is a professor of international politics at Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University, Japan. His research fields include critical security studies, sociology of knowledge, and East Asian international relations. Currently, he researches the potential of East Asian medicine as a cosmological approach to rethinking IR's metatheoretical foundations and (dis)harmony in the practice of global politics, primarily drawing on its ontological and clinical imaginaries. His recent publications appear in *International Studies Perspectives*, the *Pacific Review*, *Third World Quarterly*, *Cambridge Review of International Affairs*, and the *Czech Journal of International Relations*.

References

- Aizawa, I. (2024). Tracking the first-year experience in English medium instruction: A pre-post study of transitional challenges. *English for Specific Purposes*, 73, 20-32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2023.09.002>
- Aizawa, I., & Rose, H. (2018). An analysis of Japan's English as medium of instruction initiatives within higher education: The gap between meso-level policy and micro-level practice. *Higher Education*, 77(6), 1125-1142. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-018-0323-5>
- Aizawa, I., Rose, H., McKinley, J., & Thompson, G. (2024). A comparison of content learning outcomes between Japanese and English medium instruction. *Language and Education*, 38(6), 911-930. <https://doi.org.simsrad.net.ocs.mq.edu.au/10.1080/09500782.2023.2238688>
- Aizawa, I., Rose, H., Thompson, G., & Curle, S. (2023). Beyond the threshold: Exploring English language proficiency, linguistic challenges, and academic language skills of Japanese students in an English medium instruction programme. *Language Teaching Research*, 27(4), 837-861. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168820965510>

- Ball, P., & Lindsay, D. (2013). Language demands and support for English-medium instruction in tertiary education. Learning from a specific context. In A. Doiz, D. Lasagabaster, & J. M. Sierra (Eds.), *English-medium instruction at universities: Global challenges* (pp. 44-63). Multilingual Matters.
- Botha, W., Bolton, K., & Bacon-Shone, J. (2023). EMI (English-medium instruction) in Singapore's major universities. *World Englishes*, 42(3), 447-464. <https://doi-org.simsrad.net.ocs.mq.edu.au/10.1111/weng.12624>
- Bradford, A. (2016). Toward a typology of implementation challenges facing English-medium instruction in higher education: Evidence from Japan. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 20(4), 339-356. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315316647165>
- Bradford, A. (2019). It's not all about English! The problem of language foregrounding in English-medium programmes in Japan. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 40(8), 707-720. <https://doi-org.simsrad.net.ocs.mq.edu.au/10.1080/01434632.2018.1551402>
- Chen, C.-C., & Krickel-Choi, N.-C. (2024). Reimagining IR's biomedical foundations: East Asian medicine and the need for cosmological plurality. *Cambridge Review of International Affairs*, online first. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09557571.2024.2417057>
- Csizér, K., & Dörnyei, Z. (2005). The internal structure of language learning motivation and its relationship with language choice and learning effort. *The Modern Language Journal*, 89(1), 19-36.
- Dang, S. (2023). Multilingual practice and multilingual selves: A mixed-method study of EMI international students in Japan. *Australian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 6(2), 58-72. <https://doi.org/10.29140/ajal.v6n2.1001>
- Dearden, J. (2014). *English as a medium of instruction—a growing global phenomenon*. British Council. https://www.britishcouncil.es/sites/default/files/british_council_english_as_a_medium_of_instruction.pdf
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. Plenum Press.

- Forbes-Mewett, H., & Nyland, C. (2012). Funding international student support services: Tension and power in the university. *Higher Education, 65*(2), 181-192. [10.1007/s10734-012-9537-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-012-9537-0)
- Galloway, N., & Curle, S. (2022). "I just wanted to learn Japanese and visit Japan": The incentives and attitudes of international students in English-Medium Instruction programmes in Japan. *International Journal of Language Studies, 16*(2), 23-48. <https://eprints.gla.ac.uk/265835/1/265835.pdf>
- Galloway, N., & Rose, H. (2015). *Introducing English-medium instruction at university: Global challenges*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Galloway, N., & Ruegg, R. (2020). The provision of student support on English medium instruction programmes in Japan and China. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes, 45*, [10.1016/j.jeap.2020.100846](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2020.100846)
- Gardner, R. C., & Lambert, W. E. (1972). *Attitudes and motivation in second-language learning*. Newbury House.
- Hadingham, O. (2023). The academic literacy journey of student writers at transition to an English Medium Instruction (EMI) university programme in Japan. *Australian Journal of Applied Linguistics, 6*(2), 114-129. <https://doi.org/10.29140/ajal.v6n2.1056>
- Hino, N. (2017). The significance of EMI for the learning of EIL in higher education: Four cases from Japan. In B. Fenton-Smith, P. Humphreys & I. Walkinshaw (Eds.), *English medium instruction in higher education in Asia-Pacific: From policy to pedagogy* (pp. 115-131). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-51976-0_7
- Huang, W.-C. (2025). Transforming self-identity in EMI: The interplay of behavioral engagement, motivational intensity, and self-efficacy. *Education Sciences, 15*(4), 429. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15040429>
- Karabay, A., & Durrani, N. (2024). The evolution of English Medium Instruction research in higher education: A bibliometric study. *Education Sciences, 14*(9), 982. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14090982>
- Kim, V., & Thompson, G. (2022). The interplay between gender and major on content knowledge and self-beliefs in the English-medium instruction context: A comparative study between university students from Japan and South Korea. *System, 107*, 102824. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2022.102824>

- Kojima, N. (2016). The present state of English-medium instruction (EMI) classes: Understanding learners' motivation through preparation classes for EMI lessons [in Japanese]. *Doshisha University Annual Report from the Center for Learning Support and Faculty Development*, 7, 25-41.
- Kojima, N. (2019). Educational practices and learning environments required for English-Medium Instruction (EMI): From the perspective of motivating Japanese students. *Asia Pacific Studies (APU) Journal of Language Research*, 14, 49-64. https://doi.org/10.34409/apujlr.4.0_49
- Kojima, N. (2021). *Student motivation in English-medium instruction: Empirical studies in a Japanese university*. Routledge.
- Kojima, N., & Yashima, T. (2017). Motivation in English medium instruction classrooms from the perspective of self-determination theory and the ideal self. *JACET Journal*, 61, 23-39. https://doi.org/10.32234/jacetjournal.61.0_23
- Kuteeva, M., & Kaufhold, K. (2024). An 'E' for 'elite' in EMI? Global, local and elite dimensions in the promotion of English-medium university programmes. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01434632.2024.2393707>
- Macaro, E., Curle, S., & Pun, J., An, J., & Dearden, J. (2018). A systematic review of English medium instruction in higher education. *Language Teaching*, 51, 36-76. <http://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444817000350>.
- Qiu, Y., Zheng, Y., & Liu, J. (2023). 'So, only relying on English is still troublesome': A critical examination of Japan's English medium instruction policy at multiple levels. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 44(7), 608-625. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01434632.2022.2100402>
- Rose, H., & McKinley, J. (2018). Japan's English-medium instruction initiatives and the globalization of higher education. *Higher Education*, 75, 111-129. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-017-0125-1>
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55(1), 68-78. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.55.1.68>

- Sato, T. (2022). Reconsidering Englishization: The Japanese government's Top Global University Project. *Asian Englishes*, 24(1), 102-113. <https://doi-org.simsrad.net.ocs.mq.edu.au/10.1080/13488678.2021.1902676>
- Shao, L., & Rose, H. (2024). Teachers' experiences of English-medium instruction in higher education: A cross case investigation of China, Japan and the Netherlands. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 45(7), 2801-2816. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01434632.2022.2073358>
- Thompson, G., Curle, S., & Aizawa, I. (2022). It's worth the extra effort: Behind student perceptions of success in the study of content via English-Medium Instruction in Japan. In J. McKinley & N. Galloway (Eds.), *English-Medium Instruction Practices in Higher Education: International Perspectives* (p. 213). Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Toh, G. (2024). English-medium instruction in higher education in Japan. In K. Bolton, W. Botha & B. Lin (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of English-medium instruction in higher education* (pp. 491-503). Routledge.
- Zheng, Q., & Choi, T. H. (2024). English-medium instruction as an internationalisation strategy at a second-tier Chinese University: Instructors' challenges and their shaping factors. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Second and Foreign Language Education*, 9(1), 76. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40862-024-00295-9>

Appendix A: The Questionnaire

Phase 1: Motivation Toward English Learning (Q1-Q8)

- Q1 I study English more frequently than my classmates.
- Q2 I am determined to improve my English proficiency in some form even after graduating from university.
- Q3 I believe that using English is important for me when considering my future.
- Q4 In my current environment, it does not matter much if I am not proficient in English.
- Q5 I learn English because I want to earn a higher income in the future.
- Q6 I believe that English is necessary for the profession I am aiming to pursue.
- Q7 I think learning English is beneficial for becoming the kind of global professional I aspire to be.
- Q8 I study English because I find it enjoyable to increase my skills and knowledge in the language.

Phase 2: Learning Strategies and Preparation (Q9-Q16) for EMI

Q9 I have a sufficient understanding of the technical terms used in the course materials.

Q10 I always read the assigned or distributed texts in advance to prepare for the next class.

Q11 I have a strong desire to fully understand 100% of the course content.

Q12 I always organize information in my notebook to better understand the course content.

Q13 Although I study diligently through preparation and review, my test scores are not high.

Q14 Despite engaging in preparation and review, I am very anxious about potentially receiving poor grades.

Q15 Even though I prepare and review the material, I still do not understand the course content.

Q16 I have analyzed my own learning strategies and study plans in order to succeed in this course.

Phase 3: Academic Goals and Attitudes Toward EMI (Q17-Q23)

Q17 I take this course because I need to earn credits required for graduation.

Q18 I study because it is a requirement set by the university.

Q19 I learn English in order to obtain a higher income in the future.

Q20 I believe this course is beneficial for becoming the globally competent individual I aspire to be.

Q21 I want to acquire subject-specific knowledge in English that will be useful in the future.

Q22 I find it enjoyable to increase my subject-specific knowledge through English.

Q23 To be honest, I do not care about courses taught in English in my major.

Phase 4: Perceived Difficulty and Classroom Experience (Q24-Q29)

Q24 I feel pressure about whether I will be able to earn credit for this course.

Q25 I become confused in class because I do not understand what the instructor is saying.

Q26 I tend to postpone assignments because I cannot understand the content even after reading the textbook or my notes.

Q27 The difficulty level of the assigned textbook is appropriate.

Q28 The amount of coursework assigned is appropriate.

Q29 Because I do not understand the technical terms in the textbook, I ask the instructor for clarification during class.

Q30 To what extent do you understand this lecture? Please select the number that best applies.